

ISic0794

I.Sicily inscription 0794

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε Καλή πρε(σ)β(ῦτις)
2. ζήσ(ασ)α ἔτη ν ἀμέπτως ἀμέπτως
3. τὸν βίον τελε(ευτᾶ) τῆ πρ(ὸ) ιθ κ(αλα)ν(δῶν)
4. Ὀκτωβρίων

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493900

EDR 140959

EDCS 41300019

PHI 175606

PHI 175607

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 175-176

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.

Vatican. At no.473

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